

Polymerization of Methacrylamide Initiated by Ceric Ion-Malic Acid Redox System

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The homogeneous polymerization of methacrylamide (M) was studied in aqueous sulphuric acid medium at $35 \pm 0.2^\circ$ under a nitrogen atmosphere. The rate of monomer disappearance was proportional to $[MA]^1 [Ce(IV)]^1 [M]^{1.5}$ and the rate of ceric ion disappearance was directly proportional to $[Ce(IV)]$ but independent of $[M]$. The rate increased very slowly upto a certain range of malic acid (MA) concentration above which it remained constant. A very stable complex was revealed by Lineweaver-Burk plot of $rate^{-1}$ vs $[MA]^{-1}$. Increasing reaction temperature increased the rate from 25 to 45° . The activation energy was found to be $15.25 \text{ k cal mol}^{-1}$. By decreasing pH of the medium the rate of polymerization decreased.

SEVERAL papers have appeared on the polymerization of acrylamide initiated by various redox systems¹⁻³. However, the polymerization of methacrylamide has not been attended to so much. Misra *et al* have investigated the polymerization of methacrylamide initiated by persulphate-thiomalic acid⁴ and persulphate-ascorbic acid⁵ redox systems. Burfield and Ng⁶ studied the polymerization of methacrylamide initiated by persulphate alone. The present investigation has been carried out with a view to throw light on the mechanism of polymerization of methacrylamide.

Experimental

Methacrylamide (E. Merck) was purified by two recrystallizations from acetone and dried under vacuum over calcium chloride. Malic acid (Reidal), ceric ammonium sulphate (Loba Chemie) and sulphuric acid (all AR or equivalent grade) were used as such. Double distilled water was used as solvent in all the experiments. The polymerization apparatus and procedure adopted was similar to that used by Misra *et al*⁵. The ceric ion concentration in the reaction system was determined by cerimetry. The reaction mixture was quenched by the addition of excess of standard ferrous ammonium sulphate and the excess of Fe(II) was determined by titrating it against standard ceric solution using ferroin as indicator.

Results and Discussion

Rate of monomer disappearance :

Malic acid dependence : The initial rate and maximum conversion increased with increasing $[MA]$ from 11.25×10^{-3} to 72.00×10^{-3} mol/l at constant $[M]$, $[Ce(IV)]$ and $[H_2SO_4]$. However, below 6.00×10^{-3} mol/l of $[MA]$ the polymerization was negligibly small. At lower $[MA]$ the production of primary radicals is very low, hence initial rate and maximum conversion are at the lowest. As $[MA]$ increases the production of primary free

radicals by interactions with ceric ion increases and hence initial rate and maximum conversion also

Fig. 1. Polymerization of methacrylamide with varying initial concentrations of malic acid at constant $[M] = 0.044 \text{ mol/l}$; $[Ce(IV)] = 0.002 \text{ mol/l}$; $[H_2SO_4] = 0.125 \text{ mol/l}$; Temp. $35 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

- = $11.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol/l}$;
- = $22.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol/l}$;
- = $36.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol/l}$;
- = $72.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol/l}$;
- = $15.75 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol/l}$;
- = $29.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol/l}$;
- = $54.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol/l}$.

increase (Fig. 1). The malic acid exponent was found to be unity which indicated a unimolecular termination mechanism.

Ceric ion dependence: The initial rate and maximum conversion increased with increasing ceric ion concentration from 25×10^{-4} to 50×10^{-4} mol/l at fixed [M], [MA] and $[H_2SO_4]$. However, above 50×10^{-4} mol/l concentration of ceric ion the initial rate and maximum conversion decreased. At any fixed [MA] an increase in $[Ce(IV)]$ increases the rate of production of active free radicals from malic acid by oxidation, hence rate and maximum conversion increased. Above 50×10^{-4} mol/l of $[Ce(IV)]$ the initial rate decreased showing that at higher $[Ce(IV)]$ the metal ion may get involved in termination reaction as well. The ceric ion exponent of unity confirmed the unimolecular termination mechanism. Several workers have reported the unimolecular termination mechanism^{7,8}. Dainton proposed that the unimolecular termination mechanism of growing chains in aqueous phase is due to the dissolved metal ions. On the other hand Palit and Konar⁹ suggested that unimolecular chain termination in heterogenous media may be due to degradative chain transfer, or by dissolved metal ions or by the occlusion of the growing radicals in the cage of polymer coils.

Monomer dependence: Increasing [M] from 7.03×10^{-2} to 42.19×10^{-2} mol/l increased the initial rate and maximum conversion at fixed [MA], $[Ce(IV)]$ and $[H_2SO_4]$. The more the concentration of monomer the more are the chances of initiation, higher the propagation magnitude and hence higher the initial rate and maximum conversion. The monomer exponent of near unity (1.2) rules out the possibility of primary radical termination. The samples of the polymethacrylamide formed became insoluble due to which the degree of polymerization could not be determined. The insolubility of the polymer samples is probably due to the intermolecular imidization or due to crosslinking in the polymer chains.

Temperature dependence: The effect of temperature on the rate was studied within the range 25 to 45°. As the temperature increases the initial rate and maximum conversion increased which is due to the increased frequency of initiation that enhances the rate and maximum conversion. The activation energy was found to be $15.25 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.

Sulphuric acid dependence: Increasing sulphuric acid concentration decreased the rate of polymerization at fixed [M], [MA] and $[Ce(IV)]$. This is possibly due to the formation of a highly sulphated complex of ceric ion that predominates at higher $[H_2SO_4]$. This highly sulphated complex of ceric ion has been suggested to be less reactive¹⁰. This was also proved in our laboratory by carrying out reactions with ceric ion in aqueous and sulphuric acid solutions. The rate in case of freshly prepared aqueous solutions of ceric ion are always higher than the rates observed in case of same concentration of ceric ion in sulphuric acid. By postulating $Ce(SO_4)_2$ to be the reactive species it is evident that as

$[H_2SO_4]$ is increased the HSO_4^- ions produced will compete with the malic acid molecules by acting as ligands, and hence initial rate and maximum conversion should decrease. Further, it is known that ceric ion associates successively with one, two, three and four sulphate ions to form complexes which render the ceric ion almost inactive.

Fig. 2. Plot of $-\frac{d[Ce(IV)]}{dt} \times 10^6 \text{ mol/l s}$ vs (A)-[MA]; (B)- $[Ce(IV)]$

For (A): $[M] = 7.03 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol/l}$; $[Ce(IV)] = 2.05 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol/l}$; $[H_2SO_4] = 6.83 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol/l}$; Temp. $35 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

For (B): $[M] = 4.22 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol/l}$; $[MA] = 11.06 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol/l}$; $[H_2SO_4] = 16.39 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol/l}$; Temp. $35 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

Rate of ceric ion disappearance: The rate of ceric ion disappearance increased with increasing $[Ce(IV)]$. Plot of rate vs $[Ce(IV)]$ gave a straight line passing through the origin (Fig. 2B). The rate was found to be independent of [M]. Both these observations suggest that ceric ion participates only in the redox reaction but not in initiation or termination reactions. The rate increased slightly with increasing [MA] upto a certain range above which it remained constant (Fig. 2A). This shows a strong complex formation between ceric ion and malic acid in the reaction system that decomposes in presence of sulphuric acid to give free radicals ($R^\bullet$).

where K and k_r are the formation and decomposition constants of the complex. The complex formation was confirmed by Lineweaver-Burk plot of rate^{-1} vs $[MA]^{-1}$ which left a considerable intercept

on the ordinate. pH studies revealed a 1 : 1 complex formation between ceric ion and malic acid. The ir spectra of the complex gave a peak at 1550 cm^{-1} (a shift). No peak appeared at 1725 cm^{-1} which was observed in malic acid spectrum. This shift in the peak and a peak at 560 cm^{-1} show the possible presence of metal-oxygen bonding in the complex.

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